

Recurrent neural network pruning using dynamical systems and iterative fine-tuning

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Abstract

Network pruning techniques are widely employed to reduce the memory requirements and increase the inference speed of neural networks. This work proposes a novel RNN pruning method that considers the RNN weight matrices as collections of time-evolving signals. Such signals that represent weight vectors can be modelled using Linear Dynamical Systems (LDSs). In this way, weight vectors with similar temporal dynamics can be pruned as they have limited effect on the performance of the model. Additionally, during the fine-tuning of the pruned model, a novel discrimination-aware variation of the L2 regularization is introduced to penalize network weights (i.e., reduce the magnitude), whose impact on the output of an RNN network is minimal. Finally, an iterative fine-tuning approach is proposed that employs a bigger model to guide an increasingly smaller pruned one, as a steep decrease of the network parameters can irreversibly harm the performance of the pruned model. Extensive experimentation with different network architectures demonstrates the potential of the proposed method to create pruned models with significantly improved perplexity by at least 0.62% on the PTB

dataset and improved F1-score by 1.39% on the SQuAD dataset, contrary to other state-of-the-art approaches that slightly improve or even deteriorate models' performance.

Keywords:

Recurrent Neural Networks, Network Pruning, Linear Dynamical Systems, Regularization

1. Introduction

1 Deep Neural Networks (DNNs) have revolutionized the field of machine
2 learning due to their highly discriminative abilities and robust performance,
3 leading to their wide adoption for providing solutions to complex problems in
4 numerous fields, such as computer vision (LeCun et al., 2010) and language
5 modelling (Sundermeyer et al., 2012). Nevertheless, their sensitivity to noise
6 and missing data has led several researchers to cope with the problems of
7 stability (Wei et al., 2021), the presence of missing data (Chen et al., 2020),
8 non-Gaussian noise (Stojanovic et al., 2020) and various types of uncertain-
9 ties, such as polytropic uncertainty (Tao et al., 2021). Furthermore, the
10 advances in ICT technologies and the broader use of smartphones sparked
11 a growing demand for implementing such algorithms on embedded systems.
12 Despite their effectiveness and robustness, the use of DNNs in both powerful
13 PCs and resource constrained embedded systems is governed by serious lim-
14 itations, due to the significant demands of DNNs for computational power
15 and energy consumption. To this end, this work focuses on the compression
16 and acceleration of deep networks to reduce their memory requirements and
17 increase their inference speed.

18 In the literature, most network compression methods target the acceler-
19 ation of Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) (Chatzikonstantinou et al.,
20 2020; Ding et al., 2019; Liu et al., 2019) due to their importance in im-
21 age processing applications. Lately, with the advent of Industry 4.0 and
22 the growing demand for sequence processing algorithms, techniques to ac-
23 celerate Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) (Rumelhart et al., 1986) have
24 gained attention. RNNs and their variants, such as Long Short-Term Memory
25 (LSTM) networks (Hochreiter & Schmidhuber, 1997) and Recurrent High-
26 way Networks (RHN) (Zilly et al., 2017) are capable of processing sequences
27 and capturing temporal dependencies between video frames or words in a
28 text and thus they are particularly useful in action recognition and lan-
29 guage modelling. The high accuracy of recurrent neural networks in such
30 tasks is overshadowed by their huge requirements in run-time memory and
31 their computational complexity that renders their usage in real-time applica-
32 tions inherently problematic. Moreover, the increased use of mobile devices
33 has led several deep learning networks to be implemented in such systems
34 of decreased computational resources. Therefore, there is a need towards
35 the reduction of the size and complexity of recurrent neural networks, while
36 maintaining their recognition performance.

37 Pruning the network parameters is one of the most popular compression
38 approaches, based on the assumption that many parameters in DNNs are
39 often redundant and therefore they can be removed without significantly af-
40 fecting the recognition performance of the network. Identifying redundant
41 weights in a network, however, can be a challenging task since millions of
42 mathematical operations are performed inside a network and the contribu-

43 tions from all weights are merged to produce the final output of the network.
44 Existing RNN pruning methods focus on abruptly pruning entire rows or
45 columns of the RNN weight matrices based on their magnitude (Wen et al.
46 (2018); Yu et al. (2019); Lobacheva et al. (2020)). However, such approaches
47 do not take into consideration the position of the weights in the rows or
48 columns of the weight matrices, which can carry important information (e.g.,
49 the dynamics of the data sequence), for the RNN performance. Moreover,
50 magnitude-based pruning entails the risk of removing erroneously individual
51 high magnitude weights that significantly affect the RNN output. Finally,
52 all existing pruning methods remove weights in a single step no matter the
53 pruning ratio, although an aggressive pruning can severely deteriorate the
54 performance of RNNs beyond recovery.

55 Deviating from previous work that filter weights based on their magni-
56 tudes (Lobacheva et al., 2020; Yu et al., 2019; Wen et al., 2018, 2020), the
57 proposed method considers the rows and columns of the RNN weight matrices
58 as time-evolving signals. In this way, the proposed method takes into consid-
59 eration not only the magnitude but also the position and the sequencing of
60 the weights in the weight matrices, leading to a more informative selection of
61 weights to prune and a more robust compressed representation of the weight
62 matrices. Moreover, a novel RNN structured pruning method is proposed
63 that iteratively prunes and fine-tunes RNN models with increasing pruning
64 ratios. The use of an iterative pruning scheme is based on the belief that an
65 aggressive pruning can severely degrade the performance of a network as the
66 remaining weights cannot accurately adapt their weights to compensate for
67 the loss of the pruned weights. On the other hand, pruning weights gradually

68 while fine-tuning the pruned model can assist the model to retain or even
69 improve its performance with respect to the original model. Finally, during
70 the fine-tuning of the pruned model, a discrimination-aware variation of the
71 traditional L_2 regularization is proposed, aiming to shrink network weights
72 based on their contribution to the RNN output. The aim is to avoid the uni-
73 form weight shrinking achieved by the traditional L_2 regularization, allowing
74 the pruned model to better adapt its remaining weights to compensate for
75 the pruned ones. More specifically, the main contributions of this work are
76 summarized as follows:

- 77 • A novel pruning method is proposed considering the rows and columns
78 of the RNN weight matrices as time-evolving signals modelled by linear
79 dynamical systems. The aim is to cluster signals, i.e., weight vectors,
80 and prune the ones with similar temporal dynamics, which have limited
81 effect on the performance of the model.
- 82 • Contrary to the traditional L_2 regularization that shrinks uniformly
83 all weights, this work proposes a discrimination-aware variation of the
84 L_2 regularization, whose purpose is to shrink redundant weights more
85 strongly than significant ones during fine-tuning. This is achieved by
86 comparing the RNN output at different time steps and introducing the
87 difference as a weight to the L_2 regularization, in order to reduce the
88 magnitude of weights with low discriminative ability.
- 89 • A novel iterative fine-tuning scheme is proposed that allows a pruned
90 model to achieve similar or even improved performance with respect to
91 the original one by better adapting its weights and compensate for the

92 loss of the pruned weights. Instead of aggressively pruning all weights
93 at once, the proposed scheme iteratively prunes a model with increasing
94 pruning ratio and then fine-tunes the current pruned model using the
95 guidance of the model of the previous iteration.

- 96 • The proposed method is evaluated on a language modelling and a ques-
97 tion answering datasets using three different recurrent models achieving
98 state-of-the-art performance in all cases.

99 The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Relevant previous
100 work is discussed in Section 2, while the proposed method is presented in
101 Section 3. Thorough experimental analysis and extensive comparative eval-
102 uation are provided in Section 4. Finally, conclusions are drawn in Section
103 5.

104 **2. Related work**

105 In the literature, network compression and acceleration techniques
106 can be grouped into six main categories (Cheng et al., 2018; Gupta &
107 Agrawal, 2020): a) pruning methods, which aim at removing redundant net-
108 work parameters to reduce computational complexity and storage require-
109 ments (Chatzikonstantinou et al., 2020; Ding et al., 2019; Wen et al., 2018,
110 2020); b) quantization methods that aim to quantize network parameters (i.e,
111 reduce the number of bits needed to store weights) (Wang et al., 2018; Xu
112 et al., 2018; Zhang et al., 2018); c) knowledge-distillation or teacher-student
113 methods that are based on the notion of training a shallow student network
114 to mimic a larger pretrained teacher network (Anil et al., 2018; Bhardwaj

115 et al., 2019; Zagoruyko & Komodakis, 2016); d) parameter sharing methods
116 that reduce the model size by sharing the same weights between different
117 weight blocks (Li et al., 2016; Ling et al., 2015; Ullrich et al., 2017); e)
118 low-rank approximation methods that make use of decomposition techniques
119 to split the weight matrices into smaller ones in order to reduce the com-
120 putational complexity of the network (Gusak et al., 2019; Tjandra et al.,
121 2017; Ye et al., 2018); f) compact network design strategies that construct
122 low-complexity network architectures at the expense of a small classification
123 performance reduction (e.g., replacement of fully connected layers with global
124 average pooling operators (Sandler et al., 2018), use of depthwise separable
125 convolutions (Lin et al., 2013), etc.).

126 Pruning the network parameters is one of the most popular compression
127 approaches aiming at removing network parameters based on the assumption
128 that many of them are often redundant and thereby they do not significantly
129 affect the output of the network. Pruning methods can be further classified as
130 structured or unstructured depending on the scheme that is followed during
131 parameter pruning.

132 *2.1. Unstructured pruning methods*

133 Unstructured pruning methods prune individual network parameters
134 without relying on the structure of weight matrices (i.e., channels, rank,
135 neurons, etc.). As a result, unstructured methods achieve a high pruning
136 ratio, but the pruned weight matrices are irregularly sparse leading to inef-
137 ficient computations and diminishing the benefits in run-time memory and
138 speed (Gale et al., 2020). To overcome this, special software implemen-
139 tations have been developed to efficiently perform sparse matrix computa-

140 tions (Kanellopoulos et al., 2019; Lagunas, 2020).

141 Early research works were focused on the development of unstructured
142 pruning methods. Han et al. (2015) trained a network using the L_2 regu-
143 larization to learn which connections are important and used this informa-
144 tion to prune network parameters with magnitude lower than a threshold.
145 Then fine-tuning is applied so as the remaining connections can recompense
146 for the removed ones. In Han et al. (2017), a three-step compression frame-
147 work was proposed, employing pruning, quantization and Huffman encoding.
148 Weights are pruned based on their magnitude. Then, the remaining weights
149 are uniformly quantized and, finally, Huffman encoding is applied to benefit
150 from the biased distribution of the remaining weights. Furthermore, Narang
151 et al. (2017) introduced a binary mask for each weight in the network, ini-
152 tially set to one. The mask was updated after each iteration using different
153 hyperparameters for each layer. Subsequently, this mask was used to prune
154 redundant network weights. Finally, the effect of weight initialization in
155 magnitude-based pruned LSTM networks was studied in Yu et al. (2020),
156 concerning the domains of natural language processing (NLP) and reinforce-
157 ment learning (RL). The authors proposed the “winning ticket” initialization
158 and showed that sparsified subnetworks initialized as winning tickets achieve
159 a better performance compared to randomly initialized subnetworks.

160 *2.2. Structured pruning methods*

161 Structured pruning methods prune groups of network parameters after
162 taking into consideration the structure of weight matrices. Structured prun-
163 ing methods achieve a lower pruning ratio, which has a direct effect on
164 the computational complexity and memory footprint of the model. Filter-

165 pruning methods have been widely employed to structurally prune CNN fil-
166 ters. In particular, Ding et al. (2019) proposed a Stochastic Gradient Descent
167 (SGD) optimization method that creates identical filters during training. All
168 but one identical filters are pruned with minimum accuracy loss. On the
169 other hand, You et al. (2019) multiplied the output of each filter with a
170 trainable parameter, taking advantage of the Taylor expansion to estimate
171 the change in the loss function. The less important filters were pruned based
172 on the modification of the loss function. Furthermore, Chatzikonstantinou
173 et al. (2020) proposed a magnitude based approach that prunes the filters
174 whose weight follow the Gaussian distribution, considering their contribu-
175 tion to the filter output to be insignificant. Moreover, auxiliary MSE losses
176 were used during fine-tuning to facilitate the convergence of the network.
177 In Li et al. (2020) several subnetworks were extracted based on pre-defined
178 constraints. Then, a scheme of adaptive batch normalization was applied to
179 choose the best candidate in terms of accuracy.

180 On the other hand, vector-level pruning methods have lately gained trac-
181 tion especially for recurrent neural network pruning. Mao et al. (2017) stud-
182 ied the effect of different granularity levels (i.e., fine-grained, kernel-level,
183 vector-level and filter-level) at the network’s performance. Wen et al. (2018)
184 used the group Lasso regularization to encourage sparsity and pruned the
185 vectors with values lower than a threshold. Furthermore, Yu et al. (2019)
186 handled the imbalance of the information carried by the memory cell com-
187 pared to the one carried by the hidden states by zeroing out the output gates
188 of the hidden states using the L_1 norm. In Lobacheva et al. (2020), the rows
189 of the network weight matrices that fall below a threshold were marked as

190 constant and thus were pruned. This method was also applied on top of the
191 method proposed in Wen et al. (2018). Furthermore, Wen et al. (2020) intro-
192 duced two binary “gate” variables that control the sparsity of each dimension
193 of each weight matrix. Contrary to Wen et al. (2018), L_0 regularization was
194 used to induce sparsity. Yuan et al. (2021) built a discrete space to explore
195 different architectures of various complexities ending up to a final computa-
196 tionally efficient architecture that was chosen based on accuracy and sparsity
197 objectives. Finally, Fedorov et al. (2020) employed structured pruning and
198 quantization to generate speech enhancement recurrent models that meet
199 specific requirements to run on microcontroller units. Vectors of weights were
200 pruned if their magnitude was smaller than a learnable threshold. Moreover,
201 a binary neuron was introduced that controls the update of the cell and the
202 hidden state of LSTMs.

203 The method proposed in this paper can be classified as a structured
204 vector-level pruning method. Unlike previous works that mainly rely on
205 magnitude-based pruning, the proposed method treats each vector of the
206 weight matrices (i.e., row or column) as a time-evolving signal with each
207 weight in the vector playing a specific and important role for the computa-
208 tion of the temporal dynamics of the signal.

209 **3. Proposed methodology**

210 The basic steps of the proposed RNN pruning methodology are illustrated
211 in Figure 1, where it can be seen that the main contributions of this work
212 are located in the pruning and fine-tuning phases, working complementary
213 to improve the efficiency of the proposed method. More specifically, the

Figure 1: [Best viewed in color] Flowchart of the proposed RNN pruning methodology.

214 pruning phase is responsible for the modelling, clustering and pruning of RNN
 215 weight vectors, while the fine-tuning phase is responsible for re-training the
 216 pruned model to fine-tune its weights and improve its performance. Finally,
 217 the proposed iterative scheme is a repetition of the pruning and fine-tuning
 218 phases with increasing pruning ratios until a satisfactory pruning ratio is
 219 achieved.

220 *3.1. RNN weight matrices as collections of time-evolving signals*

221 The pruning phase of the proposed methodology deals with the identi-
 222 fication of the network parameters that do not contribute significantly to
 223 the output of the network. To achieve this, this work considers the rows
 224 and columns of the weight matrices of a recurrent neural network as discrete
 225 samples of time-evolving signals. Identifying and discarding signals with
 226 similar dynamics can significantly reduce the size and memory footprint of a
 227 recurrent neural network without affecting its performance.

228 Although the proposed methodology can be easily adopted to any type
 229 of RNNs, such as Gated Recurrent Units (GRUs) and Recurrent Highway
 230 Networks (RHNs), the analysis below is mainly concentrated on Long Short-
 231 Term Memory (LSTM) units, which is probably the most widely employed
 232 RNNs to date. The architecture of an LSTM, along with the operations
 233 performed inside the network, are shown in Fig. 2. Moreover, the internal
 234 input, forget, output and update weight matrices of the LSTM are shown in
 235 Eq. 1, along with their correlations with the input and hidden state vectors
 236 of the LSTM.

$$\begin{aligned}
 i_t &= \sigma(x_t W_{xi} + h_{t-1} W_{hi} + b_i) \\
 f_t &= \sigma(x_t W_{xf} + h_{t-1} W_{hf} + b_f) \\
 o_t &= \sigma(x_t W_{xo} + h_{t-1} W_{ho} + b_o) \\
 u_t &= \tanh(x_t W_{xu} + h_{t-1} W_{hu} + b_u)
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{1}$$

237 An LSTM unit consists of three different gates, the input gate (i_t), the
 238 forget gate (f_t) and the output gate (o_t) and the cell update (u_t) (Eq. 1).
 239 The forget gate decides which part of the cell state is important and which

Figure 2: [Best viewed in color] A diagram of the operations performed inside an LSTM. The LSTM receives the input x_t at time t and the cell and hidden states c_{t-1} and h_{t-1} at time $t - 1$ and outputs the cell and hidden states c_t and h_t , respectively, at time t . The forget, input and output gates, as well as the input update step are represented as f_t , i_t , o_t and u_t , respectively.

240 can be ignored. The input gate decides which values of the cell state will be
 241 updated and the cell update creates the vector which will be added to the
 242 cell state. Finally, the output gate defines the parts of the cell state that will
 243 be part of the next hidden state.

244 From Eq. 1, it can be observed that the sizes of the weight matrices
 245 are correlated with each other in order for the LSTM equations to hold.
 246 More specifically, removing a single row from a weight matrix of the input
 247 vector W_{xk} , where $k \in \{i, f, o, u\}$) requires the reduction of the rows of all
 248 weight matrices of the input vector by one. The same holds for the weight
 249 matrices of the hidden state vector W_{hk} , where $k \in \{i, f, o, u\}$). On the
 250 other hand, removing a single column from a weight matrix of the input or

Figure 3: [Best viewed in color] Correlations among the shapes of the LSTM weight matrices. The removal of rows or columns from a single weight matrix should be followed by the removal of rows or columns from other weight matrices as well. The rows and columns in case of single matrices are transformed to planes when the matrices are stacked together.

251 hidden state vector should be followed by the reduction of the columns of
 252 the corresponding weight matrix of the hidden state or input vector by one,
 253 respectively. In other words, if a column from the weight matrix of the input
 254 vector W_{xf} is removed, then a column from the weight matrix of the hidden
 255 state vector W_{hf} needs to be discarded as well. These correlations among
 256 the weights of a weight matrix and among the weight matrices of the input
 257 and hidden state vectors are visualized in Fig. 3.

258 3.2. Network pruning

259 Developing an optimal weight pruning technique is crucial as the network
 260 size reduction should not be accompanied by a large performance degrada-
 261 tion. To this end, the proposed network pruning method considers the
 262 modelling of rows and columns of RNN weight matrices as time-evolving

263 signals. The aim is to discard similar sequences of weights, i.e., columns or
264 rows, as they do not offer any novel knowledge to the RNN network. In other
265 words, these sequences of weights do not affect significantly the performance
266 of the network. To model the sequences of weights, a linear dynamical sys-
267 tem (LDS) (Doretto et al., 2003; Ravichandran et al., 2012), which can be
268 considered as a first order ARMA process with white zero mean independent
269 and identically distributed Gaussian input, is employed. LDSs have been
270 successfully employed in several video classification applications that require
271 the modeling of time series (Dimitropoulos et al., 2014, 2016a,b), but this
272 is the first time they are leveraged in RNNs for the task of modelling the
273 temporal dynamics of the sequences of weight parameters that comprise the
274 RNN weight matrices.

275 The number of weight matrices can vary based on the type of RNNs, with
276 LSTM units consisting of 8 matrices, while RHN and GRU units consisting
277 of 6 matrices. To model the weight matrices as a collection of time-evolving
278 signals, one can either consider each matrix individually (Fig. 3(a)) or stack
279 them together in 3D blocks. The motivation behind the stacking of matrices
280 in blocks lies in the relationship among the weight matrices, as described in
281 the previous section. In the case of LSTM units, one can either consider two
282 blocks of sizes $N \times H \times 4$ and $H \times H \times 4$ (Fig. 3(b)) by stacking the weight
283 matrices of the input and hidden state vectors, respectively, or consider a
284 single block of size $H \times H \times 8$ (Fig. 3(c)) by stacking all weight matrices
285 together given that the size of the input vector N equals the number of LSTM
286 hidden units H . In this work, stacking all matrices together is proposed due
287 to the inherent interactions among the weight matrices. However, all weight

Figure 4: [Best viewed in color] The proposed technique for the pruning of RNN weight matrices from $N \times H$ to $K_r \times K_c$.

288 matrix stacking options are experimentally evaluated in Section 4.3.1.

289 From the previous analysis and based on the selected weight matrix stack-
 290 ing, the block of the LSTM weight matrices can be described as follows:

$$W \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times H \times D}, D \in \{1, 4, 8\} \quad (2)$$

291 After having defined the structure of matrix W , the goal is to reduce the
 292 number of weight parameters and increase the training and inference speed of
 293 LSTMs, as shown in Fig. 4. More specifically, initially each row $W_{ri} \in \mathbb{R}^{H \times D}$
 294 of the block W (plane if $D > 1$) with $i \in [0, N]$ is treated as a signal with a
 295 temporal dimension of H and feature space D . This means that each column
 296 $w_{rc} \in \mathbb{R}^{D \times 1}$ of W_{ri} is considered as a temporal instance of the signal that
 297 evolve in time. In a similar fashion, each column $W_{cj} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times D}$ of the block
 298 W with $j \in [0, H]$ is treated as a signal with a temporal dimension of N

299 and feature space D . From now on, the indices i and j from the row W_{ri}
 300 and column W_{cj} of the block of weight matrices W are dropped for a clearer
 301 presentation. For each row or column of the block W , an ARMA model is
 302 formulated and modelled with a LDS using the equations below:

$$z(t+1) = Az(t) + Bv(t) \quad (3)$$

303

$$w_{rc} = \bar{w}_{rc} + Cz(t) + s(t) \quad (4)$$

304

$$\bar{w}_{rc} = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{H} \sum_{k=1}^H W_r(k), & \text{if row of } W \\ \frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N W_c(k), & \text{if column of } W \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

305 In Eq. 3-5, $z(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{D \times 1}$ refers to the hidden state of the LDS at time t ,
 306 while the quantities $s(t)$ and $Bv(t)$ are the measurement and process noise,
 307 respectively and they are considered to be equal to zero in this case. The
 308 quantities used to describe the LDS are the matrix $A \in \mathbb{R}^{D \times D}$ that models
 309 the dynamics of the hidden state of the LDS and the matrix $C \in \mathbb{R}^{D \times D}$ that
 310 maps the hidden state to the output of the system.

311 In this way, every row or column of the block of weight matrices W can
 312 be described by a pair of matrices $M = (A, C)$, which is a descriptor that
 313 incorporates information on the dynamics and the values of the signal incor-
 314 porated in the row or column of W , respectively. To estimate the parameters
 315 of the LDS descriptor (i.e., pair of matrices M) a principal component based
 316 approach was proposed by Doretto et al. (2003). Based on this approach, a
 317 matrix Y is formed as shown below:

$$Y = \begin{cases} [W_r(1) - \bar{w}_{rc}, W_r(2) - \bar{w}_{rc}, \dots, W_r(H) - \bar{w}_{rc}], & \text{if row of } W \\ [W_c(1) - \bar{w}_{rc}, W_c(2) - \bar{w}_{rc}, \dots, W_c(N) - \bar{w}_{rc}], & \text{if column of } W \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

318 The average quantity \bar{w}_{rc} is defined as in Eq. 4. Then, a singular value
319 decomposition of the matrix Y is performed as $Y = USV^T$. The matrix C is
320 easily computed as $C = U$, while, given that $Z = [z(1), z(2), \dots, z(M)] = SV^T$
321 and $M = H$ or $M = N$ for a row or column of the block of weight matrices
322 W , respectively, the matrix A is computed using least squares as:

$$A = \begin{cases} [z(2), z(3), \dots, z(H)][z(1), z(2), \dots, z(H-1)]^+, & \text{if row of } W \\ [z(2), z(3), \dots, z(N)][z(1), z(2), \dots, z(N-1)]^+, & \text{if column of } W \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

323 The symbol $+$ in Eq. 7 is used to define the pseudoinverse of the matrix
324 that is applied to. After the modelling of the rows and columns of the block
325 of weight matrices W using time-evolving signals, a way to identify signals
326 with similar dynamics is required. To this end, a k-medoid algorithm is
327 employed to cluster signals based on their dynamics and identify the most
328 representative signals, which are the medoids of the clusters. In this way,
329 the aim is to discard all signals of a cluster, except its medoid that it is
330 assumed to hold enough information to characterize the entire cluster. The
331 purpose of retaining just the medoids of the k-medoid clustering procedure
332 is to significantly reduce the size and memory footprint of an RNN network
333 without sacrificing accuracy.

334 To achieve this, the rows are fed to a k-medoid algorithm with predefined
335 K_r classes. In a similar fashion, the columns are fed to another k-medoid

336 algorithm with predefined K_c classes. The number of classes is determined
 337 by the percentage of network pruning that needs to be achieved, as the rows
 338 and columns of the weights matrices are replaced by the K_r and K_c medoids
 339 of the clusters, respectively. This means that the weight matrices of the input
 340 and hidden state vectors are pruned to the sizes of $K_r \times K_c$, while it holds
 341 that $K_r = K_c$ in the case of the weight matrices that refer to the hidden
 342 state vector. To perform k-medoid clustering, a similarity metric to compare
 343 LDS descriptors and measure their distances is required. However, the LDS
 344 descriptors do not lie in the Euclidean space as each descriptor M is defined
 345 by a pair of matrices. To overcome this problem, one family of distances
 346 that is usually employed in the literature is based on subspace angles. Given
 347 two LDS descriptors, $M_1 = (A_1, C_1)$ and $M_2 = (A_2, C_2)$, the subspace angles
 348 between them are computed by first solving for P the Lyapunov equation
 349 $A^T P A - P = -C^T C$, where

$$P = \begin{bmatrix} P_{11} & P_{12} \\ P_{21} & P_{22} \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{2D \times 2D} \quad (8)$$

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} A_1 & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & A_2 \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{2D \times 2D} \quad (9)$$

$$C = \begin{bmatrix} C_1 & C_2 \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{D \times 2D} \quad (10)$$

352 After solving the above Lyapunov equation, the distance between the two
 353 LDS descriptors is defined using the Martin's distance d_M , as shown below:

Figure 5: [Best viewed in color] Outline of the proposed network fine-tuning method with all losses, including the proposed discrimination-aware $L2$ regularization, visualized. The blue arrows depict the forward propagation, whereas the red arrows depict the backward propagation computations.

$$d_M(M_1, M_2)^2 = -\ln \left(\prod_{i=1}^D \cos^2 \theta_i \right), \quad (11)$$

where $\cos^2 \theta_i = i$ th eigenvalue $(P_{11}^{-1} P_{12} P_{22}^{-1} P_{21})$

354 Other similarity metrics have also been employed in the literature, such
 355 as the Geodesic distance (Chikuse, 2012) and the Grassmannian distance
 356 (Dimitropoulos et al., 2016b). These distances are based on the projection of
 357 the LDS descriptors to the Grassmann manifold. Experimental results with
 358 different distances are presented and discussed in Section 4.3.2.

359 *3.3. Discrimination-aware L2 regularization*

360 After the network pruning phase, the pruned network requires a fine-
 361 tuning phase in order to recover its initial performance. Auxiliary losses
 362 are often employed at this step to improve the convergence of the neural
 363 network (Chatzikonstantinou et al., 2020), as shown in Fig 5. One such loss is
 364 the L_2 regularization that prevents the network from overfitting by shrinking
 365 the network parameters uniformly (Merity et al., 2018). This work proposes
 366 a discrimination-aware variation of the L_2 regularization that is based on the
 367 assumption that if certain rows of the RNN weight matrices produce similar
 368 output at different time steps, these rows have low discriminative ability.
 369 Consequently, these rows do not affect the network convergence and their
 370 impact to the output should be reduced more aggressively than those whose
 371 impact on the RNN output is significant. The traditional L_2 regularization
 372 term is defined as:

$$L_{L2} = f_{L2} \cdot \sum_{i=1}^{C_{in}} \cdot \sum_{j=1}^{C_{out}} (w_{ij})^2, \quad (12)$$

373 where w are the filters of the output layer, f_{L2} is a factor that defines the
 374 effect of the L_2 regularization to the total loss and C_{in} and C_{out} are the input
 375 and output dimensionalities of the output layer, respectively. To examine
 376 which rows have low discriminative ability, a differential vector $O_{diff} \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times H}$,
 377 where H is equal to the RNN hidden size, is defined. Given an input sequence
 378 $\mathbf{x} = [x_1, x_2, \dots, x_{t-1}, x_t]$ and the corresponding hidden state vectors computed
 379 from a RNN, $\mathbf{h} = [h_1, h_2, \dots, h_{t-1}, h_t]$, each element of the vector O_{diff} is
 380 equal to the absolute difference between the consecutive RNN hidden states
 381 of the input sequence, averaged over time, as shown below:

$$O_{diff} = \sum_{rows} \begin{bmatrix} |h_2 - h_1| \\ |h_3 - h_2| \\ \dots \\ |h_t - h_{t-1}| \end{bmatrix} / \#rows \quad (13)$$

382 In this way, each value of the vector O_{diff} contains the mean output
 383 difference of a single hidden state. A small mean output difference indicates
 384 a low discriminative ability of the row of the RNN weight matrices responsible
 385 for computing the corresponding hidden state. During backpropagation, the
 386 gradients of the L_{L2} regularization term are multiplied by $1 \oslash O_{diff}$, where
 387 \oslash denotes the elementwise division, as shown below:

$$\left(\frac{\partial L_{L2}}{\partial W_{x*}}\right)' = 1 \oslash O_{diff} \otimes \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{\partial L_{L2}}{\partial W_{x*}}[:, i], \quad (14)$$

$$\left(\frac{\partial L_{L2}}{\partial W_{h*}}\right)' = 1 \oslash O_{diff} \otimes \sum_{i=1}^H \frac{\partial L_{L2}}{\partial W_{h*}}[:, i], \quad (15)$$

$$\left(\frac{\partial L_{L2}}{\partial W_{b*}}\right)' = 1 \oslash O_{diff} \otimes \frac{\partial L_{L2}}{\partial W_{b*}}, \quad (16)$$

390 where W_{x*} are the input matrices, W_{h*} are the hidden matrices, W_{b*} are
 391 the bias matrices, $*$ can be any of $\{f, i, u, o\}$, N is the input size, H is the
 392 hidden size of the RNN and \otimes denotes the elementwise multiplication. With
 393 this operation, the rows of the RNN weight matrices producing hidden states
 394 with small mean output difference in the vector O_{diff} and thus considered
 395 insignificant for the RNN output, generate large gradients. Due to the effect
 396 of the L_2 regularization, large gradients lead the corresponding weights of the
 397 RNN weight matrices to shrink, zeroing out their effect on the output of the
 398 RNN. Experimental results presented in Section 4.3.5 demonstrate that the

399 proposed discrimination-aware variation of the L_2 regularization outperforms
 400 the original one.

401 Moreover, a mean squared error (MSE) term is inserted after the output
 402 layer. The MSE loss can be defined as:

$$L_{MSE} = \frac{1}{C_{in}C_{out}} \cdot (S^p - S^b)^2, \quad (17)$$

403 where S^p denotes the output of the pruned network and S^b is the output of
 404 the baseline network. After considering all losses (shown in Fig. 5), the total
 405 loss becomes:

$$L_f = L_s + f_{MSE} * L_{MSE} + L_{L2}, \quad (18)$$

406 where L_s is the softmax loss and f_{MSE} is a factor that weights the impact of
 407 the MSE loss to the total loss.

408 3.4. Iterative network fine-tuning

409 In this section, a novel iterative fine-tuning approach is proposed to im-
 410 prove the convergence of the pruned network and thus its performance on a
 411 given task. As the performance of a network usually drops after the pruning,
 412 a fine-tuning phase is proposed in the literature to guide the pruned network
 413 to recover some of its lost accuracy or even improve the accuracy of the ini-
 414 tial “unpruned” network that is called baseline. However, enforcing a large
 415 pruning ratio on a network may lead the network to never fully recover its
 416 initial performance and thus achieve sub-optimal classification results.

417 Leveraging on this, an iterative fine-tuning approach is proposed that
 418 aims to make the transition between a baseline and a highly pruned network
 419 smoother, as shown in Fig. 6. To this end, the proposed network pruning
 420 technique of Section 3.2 is employed to create n pruned models, all starting

Figure 6: [Best viewed in color] Proposed iterative approach for the fine-tuning of an increasingly smaller model in each iteration based on the result of the previous iteration.

421 from the baseline model. Pruned model m_1 has the lowest pruning ratio,
 422 while model m_n has the highest pruning ratio. Then, the baseline model
 423 is used to fine-tune model m_1 , the fine-tuned model m_1 is used to fine-tune
 424 model m_2 and the same procedure continues until the fine-tuned model m_{n-1}
 425 is employed to fine-tune model m_n . In this way, the proposed approach
 426 aims to steadily decrease the number of weights of the baseline model, while
 427 allowing the pruned model to progressively adapt its weights and compensate
 428 for the loss of the pruned weights. This approach allows the pruned model

429 to achieve similar or even better performance with respect to the baseline
430 model. As shown in Section 4, the final pruned network achieves a better
431 classification performance using the proposed iterative fine-tuning procedure
432 rather than using a single fine-tuning step.

433 4. Experimental evaluation

434 This section initially presents the datasets used for the evaluation of the
435 proposed RNN pruning method. Then, an ablation study of the impact of
436 different parameters on the performance of the proposed method is presented.
437 Finally, the proposed method is compared against other state-of-the-art RNN
438 pruning methodologies.

439 4.1. Datasets and metrics

440 Two well-known publicly available datasets on natural language process-
441 ing are employed for the experimental evaluation of the proposed pruning
442 method. These datasets are selected due to being large in size and widely
443 employed in the literature for RNN pruning, rendering them crucial for the
444 training and the comparative evaluation of the proposed method.

445 Penn Treebank (PTB): The PTB dataset (Taylor et al., 2003) consists of a
446 vocabulary of 10k words, without capital letters, numbers, and punctuations
447 extracted from 2,499 stories in a three-year Wall Street Journal collection.
448 The dataset exists in both a word-level and a character-level form and in this
449 work, the word-level form is utilized. The dataset consists of 929k training,
450 73k validation and 82k test words.

451 SQuAD: The Stanford Question Answering Dataset (SQuAD) 1.1
452 dataset (Rajpurkar et al., 2016) consists of over 100k questions-answers pairs

453 that were asked by coworkers on a set of 500 Wikipedia articles. The dataset
454 tests the ability of a system to not only answer reading comprehension ques-
455 tions, but also abstain when presented with a question that cannot be an-
456 swered. The dataset consists of 87.6k training and 10.57k validation exam-
457 ples.

458 For the evaluation of the performance of the proposed method, the metrics
459 of perplexity, pruning ratio and mult-add reduction are mainly employed.
460 Perplexity measures the prediction error and it is defined as the exponential
461 of the average loss function, i.e., e^{loss} , for all samples of the test set. A smaller
462 perplexity indicates a better model and it is widely employed as an evaluation
463 metric for language models. On the other hand, the pruning ratio is equal
464 to the total number of network parameters pruned from the baseline model
465 divided by the total number of network parameters of the baseline model.
466 The mult-add reduction calculates the reduction in the number of arithmetic
467 operations performed inside the model and is computed by dividing the total
468 number of the multiplies and additions of the baseline model with the total
469 number of the multiplies and additions of the pruned model. Finally, other
470 important metrics for the comparison between pruned and baseline models
471 are the model parameters, the model size that is the size of the model when
472 saved in a hard disk, the memory size that refers to the size of run-time
473 memory the model uses during inference and the inference time that refers
474 to the time needed for the model to infer results for the entire test set.
475 Regarding the comparison with other SoTA methods, the metrics chosen for
476 the evaluation of the performance of the proposed method are the perplexity
477 for the PTB dataset and the F1 and EM metrics for the SQuAD dataset,

478 following the practice of previous literature works in order to ensure a fair
479 comparison with them.

480 *4.2. Implementation details*

481 To train, validate and test the proposed method, the following experi-
482 mental protocols were employed. The PTB dataset provides predefined data
483 splits, while the SQuAD dataset has no test set. To this end, 10% of the
484 SQuAD training set was kept aside for validation and the initial validation
485 set was used as test set, a protocol commonly used by other pruning methods
486 in the literature. The best model for each dataset is selected based on the
487 metric of perplexity achieved on the test set.

488 Regarding the PTB dataset, the big and small PTB benchmark models
489 are selected for pruning. Both models are composed of a word embedding
490 layer, 2 LSTM layers and an output linear layer with a dimension of 10000
491 that is equal to the vocabulary size of the PTB dataset. However, the big
492 PTB model has embedding and hidden sizes of 1500, while the small PTB
493 model has embedding and hidden sizes of 200. Furthermore, both PTB mod-
494 els are evaluated with and without pruning their embedding layers. Finally,
495 a RHN model that was initially proposed by Zilly et al. (2017) and imple-
496 mented by Cruz (2019) with a width of 830 and a depth of 10 is selected
497 for pruning and evaluation on the PTB dataset, while a variation of the Bi-
498 Directional Attention Flow (BiDAF) model (Kim, 2018), initially proposed
499 by Seo et al. (2017), is used for the evaluation in the SQuAD dataset. In
500 this way, the ability of the proposed method to optimally prune any type of
501 RNNs (i.e., LSTM, RHN and BLSTM) is stretched out.

502 The PTB and RHN models are trained with an initial learning rate of 20,

503 divided by 4 each time the loss is not reduced, without using any optimizer
504 algorithm. Gradient clipping is applied in order to avoid exploding gradients
505 with threshold equal to 0.25. The big PTB and the RHN models are trained
506 for 40 epochs, while the small PTB model is trained for 20 epochs. A se-
507 quence length of 35 and a batch size of 20 are used for all PTB and RHN
508 models. The dropout value varies based on the size of the model and in
509 particular, the baseline big PTB model is trained with a dropout of 0.65, the
510 pruned big PTB model without its embedding layer pruned uses a dropout
511 of 0.4, whereas the pruned big PTB model with its embedding layer pruned
512 is trained with a dropout of 0.35. On the other hand, the small PTB model
513 does not use dropout during training, while the RHN model is trained with a
514 dropout of 0.3 for the hidden units and 0.65 for the output activations. The
515 BiDAF model is trained for 12 epochs with a learning rate of 0.5 and the
516 adadelata optimizer, a batch size of 20 and a dropout for the BLSTMs equal
517 to 0.2. An exponential moving average algorithm is employed to smooth the
518 weight values. Furthermore, the parameters of every model are initialized
519 with values drawn from the uniform distribution. The values vary from -0.1
520 to 0.1 for the PTB models, from -0.04 to 0.04 for the RHN model and from
521 -0.001 to 0.001 for the BiDAF model.

522 The proposed iterative fine-tuning approach is applied to all PTB and
523 RHN models. However, it is not applied to the BiDAF model since its
524 BLSTMs are not aggressively pruned. Six pruned models are created from
525 the baseline big PTB model with hidden sizes of 1000, 700, 500, 400, 340 and
526 280, respectively. Two pruned models are created from the baseline small
527 PTB model with hidden sizes of 130 and 92. Finally, three pruned models

528 are created for the RHN model with hidden sizes of 580, 450 and 370.

529 For the training and testing of the implemented deep learning models, the
530 Python 3.5 and Pytorch (Paszke et al., 2017) (version 1.4.0) environments are
531 employed. For the computation and clustering of LDSs, the Matlab platform
532 (version 2017a) is employed. The PC used for the experiments has an Intel
533 Core i7-6700K with 4 GHz CPU, 32 GB RAM and a GeForce GTX 1070
534 GPU with 8 GB VRAM and CUDA version 10.2.

535 *4.3. Ablation study*

536 The ablation study showcases the importance of the novelties proposed
537 in this work, as well as the effect of all important hyperparameters of the
538 proposed RNN pruning method. Each novelty affects different phases of the
539 proposed method (i.e., weight matrix modelling as temporal signals affects
540 the pruning phase, discrimination-aware L_2 regularization affects the fine-
541 tuning phase, while the iterative scheme affects the entire method) and thus
542 their impact on the proposed RNN pruning method is complementary. This
543 study is performed on the test set of the PTB dataset using the big PTB
544 model with the LSTM pruned from the size of 1500 to the size of 340 and
545 without pruning its embedding layer and on the validation set of the SQuAD
546 dataset using the BiDAF model. Every experiment is conducted 5 times and
547 the mean perplexity is computed and reported.

548 *4.3.1. Impact of pruning strategies*

549 As it was previously discussed, for the RNN pruning, the weight matrices
550 can be considered either individually or stacked together in 3d blocks. Due
551 to the internal interactions among the weight matrices of an RNN, the belief

Table 1: Impact of pruning strategies on the perplexities of the big PTB and the BiDAF models.

Pruning strategy	Perplexity	
	Big PTB model (Baseline perplexity: 77.63)	BiDAF model (Baseline perplexity: 35.61)
1	84.11	31.23
4	83.71	31.17
8	83.57	n/a

552 is that stacking weight matrices in a single block carries the most descrip-
553 tive information as it allows the modelling of their in-between dependencies.
554 However, this work evaluates all logical combinations of weight matrix stack-
555 ing to find the most beneficial one. Therefore, in the case of LSTMs of the
556 PTB model, 3 different pruning strategies are tested: i) Each weight matrix
557 is considered individually (Fig. 3(a)). ii) The weight matrices are stacked
558 together in two blocks of 4 (Fig. 3(b)). iii) The weight matrices are stacked
559 together in one block of 8 (Fig. 3(c)).

560 In the case of BLSTMs of the BiDAF model, the third strategy is not
561 applicable due to the fact that the input and the hidden sizes of the BLSTMs
562 differ, i.e., the input and hidden state matrices of the BLSTMs are not equal
563 in size and thus they cannot be stacked together, as it has been discussed in
564 Section 3.2.

565 Based on the experimental results presented in Table 1, the stacking of
566 the weight matrices in the fewer possible blocks achieves the best results,

567 whereas the individual modelling of each weight matrix achieves the worst.
568 This experiment validates the belief that there are correlations among the
569 weight matrices that should be taken into consideration for the selection of
570 an optimal pruning strategy. Considering each entry of a weight matrix as a
571 feature in a unified space formed by the same entries of all weight matrices
572 (i.e., feature space of 8 values in the case of LSTMs), it is possible to achieve
573 a more accurate and robust modelling of the dynamic information present on
574 the weight matrices, while simultaneously respecting the correlations among
575 the features. For the remaining experiments of the ablation study, we con-
576 sider the optimal choices of a single block of 8 matrices for the PTB model
577 and two blocks of 4 matrices for the BiDAF model.

578 *4.3.2. Impact of LDS similarity metrics*

579 The LDS descriptors used for the modelling of the rows and columns
580 of the RNN weight matrices do not lie in the Euclidean space and thus
581 specialized similarity metrics are required to measure the distances among
582 them. Three similarity metrics are widely employed in the literature, namely
583 Martin’s, Grassmannian and Procrustes distances (Lipman et al., 2011). The
584 last two are based on the projection of the LDS descriptors to the Grassmann
585 manifold. All three metrics are evaluated and the results are illustrated in
586 Table 2. From the experimental results, it can be observed that the best
587 results are achieved using the Martin’s distance, while the use of the other
588 two metrics leads to slightly deteriorated results.

Table 2: Impact of LDS similarity metrics on the perplexities of the big PTB and the BiDAF models.

LDS similarity metric	Perplexity	
	Big PTB model (Baseline perplexity: 77.63)	BiDAF model (Baseline perplexity: 35.61)
Grassmannian	83.75	31.65
Procrustes	83.78	31.97
Martin’s	83.57	31.17

589 *4.3.3. Impact of pruning ratios*

590 Two important hyperparameters of the k-medoid algorithm are the num-
591 ber of clusters used to divide the input data and the number of iterations for
592 the convergence of the k-medoid algorithm. The k-medoid algorithm is exe-
593 cuted with different number of iterations, ranging from 50 to 400 with a step
594 of 50. The pruned big PTB and BiDAF models are then evaluated on the
595 PTB and the SQuAD dataset, respectively. The experiments are inconclu-
596 sive with no significant difference observed for different number of iterations.
597 Slightly better results are achieved when the k-medoid algorithm is executed
598 for 200 iterations and this value is adopted for all experiments.

599 On the other hand, the number of clusters has a direct effect on the
600 performance of the pruned model as it significantly affects the weight pruning
601 ratio. More specifically, Table 3 illustrates the impact of the number of
602 clusters on the pruned model perplexity, model size, memory size, inference
603 time, floating point operations (FLOPs) and iteration time that refers to the

604 average time required for a single iteration of the k-medoid LDS clustering.

605 From the experiments, it can be observed that the model and memory
606 size of the pruned model, as well as the iteration time of the k-medoid clus-
607 tering decrease linearly with the decrease of the number of clusters whereas
608 the inference time of the pruned model demonstrates an exponentially de-
609 creasing behaviour as the number of clusters decreases. On the other hand,
610 the perplexity of the pruned model increases as the number of clusters de-
611 creases, showing that the model struggles to maintain its performance when
612 the number of pruned weights increases. The selection of an appropriate
613 number of clusters depends on the pruning ratio that needs to be achieved
614 and the memory, speedup and performance specifications of each application.

615 In this work, the optimal number of clusters is determined by the prun-
616 ing ratio achieved by the literature works with which the proposed method
617 is compared. For the rest of the experiments of the ablation study, the num-
618 ber of clusters is equal to 340 for the PTB dataset. Regarding the SQuAD
619 dataset, the same hidden sizes for all three BLSTMs of the BiDAF model was
620 used for simplicity in all experiments of Table 3. In all other experiments of
621 the ablation study and the comparative evaluation, the hidden sizes of the 3
622 BLSTM layers are chosen to be equal to 26, 39 and 24 respectively, as illus-
623 trated in Table 13 for fair comparison with the state-of-the-art approaches
624 (i.e., in order to keep similar pruning ratio).

625 4.3.4. *Impact of the MSE loss factor*

626 This section evaluates the effect of the MSE loss factor f_{MSE} employed
627 during network fine-tuning to the perplexity of the pruned big PTB and
628 BiDAF models. According to the results presented in Table 4, it can be

Table 3: Number of parameters, pruning ratio, perplexity, model size, memory size, inference time, FLOPs and iteration time for the big PTB and the BiDAF models using different number of clusters.

No. of clusters	Model Parameters (M)	Pruning ratio (%)	Perplexity	Model size (MB)	Memory size (MB)	Inference time (s)	FLOPs (M)	Iteration time (s)
Big PTB model (Baseline perplexity: 77.63)								
360	22.33	66.18	83.42	89	190	0.86	44.63	119.88
340	21.84	66.92	83.57	87	185	0.77	43.65	112.84
320	21.36	67.65	84.24	86	182	0.66	42.70	106.63
300	20.89	68.36	84.35	84	179	0.63	41.76	103.83
280	20.44	69.04	84.76	82	174	0.6	40.84	97.26
260	19.99	69.73	85.45	80	170	0.58	39.94	90.85
240	19.55	70.39	86.43	78	167	0.54	39.06	84.73
BiDAF model (Baseline perplexity: 35.61)								
80	1.59	26.5	29.07	52	2805	0.240	1.74	18.83
60	1.09	49.76	32.03	50	2632	0.220	1.17	17.16
40	0.65	69.76	35.65	48	2436	0.214	0.69	15.15
20	0.29	86.50	43.81	46	2242	0.209	0.30	13.19

Table 4: Impact of the MSE loss factor on the perplexity of the big PTB and the BiDAF models.

MSE loss factor	Perplexity	
	Big PTB model (Baseline perplexity: 77.63)	BiDAF model (Baseline perplexity: 35.61)
0	83.57	31.17
0.25	77.58	28.25
0.5	76.68	26.98
0.75	76.82	26.33
1	76.96	25.49
1.25	77.35	23.9
1.5	77.77	24.67

629 concluded that the introduction of the MSE loss term significantly improves
630 the model performance as it decreases perplexity. As the value of the MSE
631 loss factor increases, the performance of the model keeps improving. How-
632 ever, there is a threshold over which the performance of the model starts
633 deteriorating. It is experimentally found that a value between 0.5 and 1.25,
634 depending on the model architecture, for the MSE loss factor f_{MSE} produces
635 optimal results as far as the perplexity of the model is concerned.

636 4.3.5. Impact of regularization techniques

637 The purpose of regularization techniques is to make small modifications
638 to the learning algorithm, enabling the model to generalize better and im-
639 prove its performance. In this work, two different regularization techniques

Table 5: Impact of regularization techniques and the proposed differential vector O_{diff} on the perplexity of the big PTB and the BiDAF models.

Regularization	Perplexity	
	Big PTB model (Baseline perplexity: 77.63)	BiDAF model (Baseline perplexity: 35.61)
No regularization	76.68	23.9
L_1 regularization	76.06	23.15
Discrimination-aware L_1 regularization	76.23	22.79
L_2 regularization	76.24	22.64
Discrimination-aware L_2 regularization	75.7	22.34

640 are evaluated, namely the L_1 and the L_2 regularization. Furthermore, the
641 discrimination-aware variations of the regularization terms, as defined in Sec-
642 tion 3.3 with the introduction of the differential vector O_{diff} are evaluated.

643 According to Table 5, all tested regularization techniques improve the
644 model perplexity. Moreover, the introduction of the differential vector O_{diff} ,
645 along with the L_2 regularization further improves the results by decreasing
646 the perplexity of the pruned big PTB model to the value of 75.7 and the
647 perplexity of the BiDAD model to the value of 22.34. These results demon-
648 strate that 9.96% of the total improvement in perplexity of the pruned big
649 PTB model and 17.67% of the total improvement in perplexity of the pruned
650 BiDAF model is attributed to the proposed discrimination-aware L_2 reg-
651 ularization. Thus, this experiment validates the importance of shrinking
652 weights, whose effect to the output of a network is considered negligible. In
653 addition, experiments are conducted, concerning the value of the factor f_{L2}
654 that controls the impact of the regularization loss term. Based on the results

Table 6: Impact of the regularization loss term factor on the perplexity of the big PTB and the BiDAF models.

Regularization loss factor	Perplexity	
	Big PTB model (Baseline perplexity: 77.63)	BiDAF model (Baseline perplexity: 35.61)
10^{-3}	94.61	24.96
10^{-4}	79.85	22.34
10^{-5}	75.7	25.11
10^{-6}	76.51	26.08
10^{-7}	76.92	26.21

655 of Table 6, the optimal value for the regularization loss term factor f_{L2} is
656 equal to $1e^{-5}$ and $1e^{-4}$ for the big PTB and the BiDAF model, respectively.
657 Higher or smaller values for the regularization loss term factor significantly
658 deteriorate the performance of the pruned models.

659 4.3.6. Evaluation of the proposed iterative network fine-tuning approach

660 In this section, the proposed iterative fine-tuning approach is evaluated
661 on the big PTB model. Five pruned models are created, all starting from the
662 baseline model with hidden sizes of 1000, 700, 500, 400, and 340, respectively.
663 Normally, the baseline model of size 1500 guides directly or in a single step
664 the fine-tuning of the targeted pruned model, which in this case has a size
665 of 340. However, in the proposed iterative approach, the baseline model is
666 used to guide the model with the lowest pruning ratio and then every model
667 guides the smaller one until the target pruning ratio is achieved.

668 As it is illustrated in Table 7, the proposed approach achieves a smaller

Table 7: Evaluation of single-step vs iterative fine-tuning on the big PTB model.

Fine-tuning approach	Steps	Pruned model perplexity
Single-step	1500→340	75.7
Iterative	1500→1000→700→500→400→340	73.73

669 perplexity of almost 2 with respect to the single-step fine-tuning approach.
 670 It is also worth noting that the pruned model using the iterative fine-tuning
 671 approach achieves a smaller perplexity even compared to the perplexity of
 672 the baseline model. This experiment validates the claim of this work that the
 673 pruning procedure should be iterative with larger and larger pruning ratios
 674 until the target is reached. Enforcing a large pruning ratio aggressively to
 675 a model can significantly deteriorate its performance beyond any recovery.
 676 Finally, Table 8 performs a direct comparison between the baseline and the
 677 pruned model in terms of perplexity, model size, memory size, inference time
 678 and FLOPs. The pruned model can generalize better (smaller perplexity) and
 679 run much faster due to its smaller size, storage size and run-time memory size,
 680 as well as its fewer floating operations (FLOPs). More specifically, the pruned
 681 model has three times less parameters, storage size, run-time memory size
 682 and FLOPs and nine times smaller execution time, compared to the baseline
 683 model. This conclusion verifies the ability of the proposed network pruning
 684 method to select and remove weights that are not only unnecessary but also
 685 frequently detrimental to the performance and generalization ability of the
 686 model.

Table 8: Comparison of baseline and pruned big PTB models in terms of perplexity, size, memory size, inference time and FLOPs.

Model	Hidden size	Perplexity	Model Parameters (M)	Model size (MB)	Memory size (MB)	inference time (s)	FLOPs (M)
Baseline	1500	77.63	66.03	264	539	6.97	132.00
Pruned	340	73.73	21.84	87	185	0.77	43.65

Table 9: Evaluation of methods on the big PTB model without pruning its embedding layer.

Method	Baseline perplexity	Pruned perplexity	Difference	Pruning ratio (%)	Hidden size	Mult-add reduction
Wen et al. (2018)	78.57	78.65	+0.08	66.89	[373, 315]	7.48×
Lobacheva et al. (2020)	78.57	77.82	-0.75	68.94	[252, 394]	-
Yu et al. (2019)	78.57	78.37	-0.20	-	[63, 375]	8.63×
Yuan et al. (2021)	78.57	78.67	+0.10	68.3	[319, 285]	7.81×
Proposed (block size: 4)	77.63	75.86	-1.77	68.3	[319, 285]	8.7×
Proposed (block size: 8)	77.63	75.25	-2.38	69.04	[280, 280]	9.41×

687 *4.4. Comparison with state-of-the-art methods*

688 The proposed method is comparatively evaluated against various state-of-
689 the-art RNN pruning methods (Lobacheva et al., 2020; Wen et al., 2018, 2020;
690 Yu et al., 2019; Yuan et al., 2021) and the results are presented below. The
691 compared baseline models are the same and any differences in their baseline
692 perplexity can be attributed to the different implementation framework (i.e.,
693 PyTorch vs Tensorflow) and the stochastic nature of the training process.

694 Initially, a comparison is made with methods that provide results in the
695 PTB dataset, using the big PTB model without pruning its embedding layer.
696 Two different models are evaluated: One model employing weight matrices

Table 10: Evaluation of methods on the small PTB model without pruning its embedding layer.

Method	Baseline perplexity	Pruned perplexity	Difference	Pruning ratio (%)	Hidden size	Mult-add reduction
Lobacheva et al. (2020)	114.41	105.64	-8.77	32.89	[64, 115]	-
Proposed (block size: 4)	113.87	101.42	-12.45	28.84	[64, 115]	2.03×
Proposed (block size: 8)	113.87	102.51	-11.36	33.33	[92, 92]	2.82×

697 stacked in one block of 8 and hidden size of 280 to achieve comparable prun-
 698 ing ratio with other approaches and one model with two blocks of 4, em-
 699 ploying the same hidden size with the best approach. From Table 9, it can
 700 be concluded that the best proposed model achieves a decreased perplex-
 701 ity by 2.38 compared to the baseline model, although with a much smaller
 702 number of parameters. Moreover, the proposed method achieves a larger
 703 decrease to the model perplexity with respect to other methods that achieve
 704 a perplexity close to the baseline model. In addition, the proposed method
 705 manages to prune a larger percentage of network parameters than the other
 706 methods. Even by using block size of 4, that is not optimal based on our
 707 ablation study, the model pruned by the proposed method achieves a larger
 708 decrease to the model perplexity compared to the other methods. Similar
 709 observations can be made by comparing the proposed method with another
 710 method that prunes the small PTB model, as shown in Table 10. These
 711 experiments demonstrate the superiority of the proposed method in identi-
 712 fying and pruning parameters without affecting the overall performance of
 713 the PTB models.

714 Contrary to the majority of the literature methods that do not prune

Table 11: Evaluation of methods on the big PTB model with its embedding layer pruned.

Method	Baseline perplexity	Pruned perplexity	Difference	Pruning ratio (%)	Hidden size	Embedding size	Mult-add reduction
Wen et al. (2020)	78.57	78.08	-0.49	90.64	[296, 247]	251	13.96×
Proposed (block size: 4)	77.63	77.01	-0.62	90.64	[296, 247]	251	13.96×
Proposed (block size: 8)	77.63	76.00	-1.63	90.68	[255, 255]	255	14.21×

715 the embedding layer, Wen et al. (2020) apply their pruning method to the
 716 embedding layer too. For fair comparison, a weight pruning method was also
 717 applied in this work by removing the weight parameters of embedding vectors
 718 starting from those with the smallest magnitude. The comparison is shown
 719 in Table 11 and reveals that the pruned model derived from the proposed
 720 method achieves a lower perplexity with a slightly larger pruning ratio than
 721 the pruned model of Wen et al. (2020). Furthermore, the proposed method
 722 achieves a larger reduction in the multiplications and the additions of the
 723 baseline model. A second model pruned by the proposed method is evaluated
 724 using the same hidden size and pruning ratio with Wen et al. (2020) that
 725 achieves an improved performance in connection with the compared method.

726 Moreover, the proposed method is evaluated on the PTB dataset using
 727 the RHN model. The results, shown in Table 12, demonstrate the ability
 728 of the proposed method to accurately prune parameters from various types
 729 of recurrent neural network. More specifically, the pruned model derived
 730 from the proposed method achieves the lowest perplexity and the largest
 731 improvement in perplexity with respect to the baseline model, while also
 732 achieving the largest pruning ratio, in comparison with the other pruning
 733 methods. Even lower perplexity but with a smaller pruning ratio achieves

Table 12: Evaluation of methods that employ the RHN model on the PTB dataset.

Method	Baseline perplexity	Pruned perplexity	Difference	Pruning ratio (%)	Width	Mult-add reduction
Wen et al. (2018)	65.4	67.7	+2.3	67.66	403	-
Wen et al. (2020)	65.4	65.1	-0.3	69.36	389	-
Proposed (width 389)	60.55	58.26	-2.29	69.36	389	2.87×
Proposed (width 370)	60.55	58.39	-2.16	75.13	370	3.07×

734 the pruned model with the same width as the model of Wen et al. (2020)

735 Finally, the proposed method is applied to the BiDAF model and evalu-
736 ated on the SQuAD dataset. This model has four bidirectional LSTM layers,
737 namely the contextual embedding layer, two modelling layers and the output
738 layer. In compliance with the previous methods, the contextual embedding
739 layer is not pruned. Table 13 presents the hidden sizes of the baseline and
740 pruned forward and backward modelling and forward and backward output
741 BLSTM layers and the total number of parameters of the aforementioned
742 layers. The implementation used in this work is slightly different from the
743 one used by Wen et al. (2018) and Wen et al. (2020) in that different word
744 and character embedding layers are employed. Therefore, only the parame-
745 ters and the parameter reduction ratio of the pruned layers are demonstrated
746 in Tables 13 and 14 for fair comparison, along with the performance of the
747 models measured in F1-score and Exact Match (EM) that computes the per-
748 centage of the correctly recognized sentences.

749 Table 14 shows that the pruned model derived from the proposed method
750 achieves a better performance than the baseline model (increased F1-score
751 and increased EM) with less than 19% of the number of parameters that the

752 initial baseline model has. On the other hand, the pruned models computed
753 from the other state-of-the-art methods demonstrate a larger drop in F1-
754 score and EM (i.e., more than 2%) with respect to the corresponding baseline
755 models. As a result, the proposed method can be successfully employed for
756 the pruning of BLSTM layers as well, significantly reducing the number of
757 parameters without deteriorating the performance of the pruned model with
758 respect to the baseline model. The pruned model is also evaluated using
759 additional commonly employed metrics (i.e., perplexity, bleu and rouge) in
760 order to encourage new works on this field to evaluate their models on them.

761 At this point, a few advantages and limitations of the proposed method
762 can be mentioned. The proposed method is appropriate for either small or
763 large datasets as the time and space complexity of the method does not scale
764 with the size of the dataset, but only with the size of the RNN weight matri-
765 ces (i.e., input, hidden state and output sizes) and the predetermined number
766 of clusters. This also means that the higher the pruning ratio, the faster the
767 proposed network pruning method runs. On the other hand, the proposed
768 method is not end-to-end, meaning that the model is initially trained and
769 the RNN weight matrices are extracted using PyTorch, then the matrices are
770 modelled using LDSs and pruned in Matlab and finally the pruned RNN ma-
771 trices are loaded to the pruned model, which is fine-tuned using PyTorch. In
772 addition, since the speed of the proposed network pruning procedure depends
773 on the size of the RNN weight matrices, it can end up being computationally
774 heavy for large matrices. Nevertheless, the proposed pruning procedure does
775 not affect the execution speed of the pruned model at all.

Table 13: Hidden sizes of the forward and backward modelling layers (ModFwd and ModBwd) and the forward and backward output layer (OutFwd and OutBwd) of the BiDAF model.

Method	ModFwd1	ModBwd1	ModFwd2	ModBwd2	OutFwd1	OutBwd1	Parameters (M)
Baseline	100	100	100	100	100	100	2.16
Wen et al. (2018)	20	33	40	38	31	16	0.41
Wen et al. (2020)	26	33	36	36	33	15	0.43
Proposed	26	26	39	39	24	24	0.40

Table 14: Evaluation of methods on the SQuAD dataset using the BiDAF model.

Method	Baseline EM/F1	Pruned EM/F1	Difference	Pruning ratio (%)	Perplexity	Bleu	Rouge
Wen et al. (2018)	67.98/77.85	65.36/75.78	-2.62/ - 2.07	81.29	-	-	-
Wen et al. (2020)	67.98/77.85	65.67/75.69	-2.31/ - 2.16	80.36	-	-	-
Proposed	65.28/76.08	63.40/74.69	+1.88/ + 1.39	81.30	22.34	21.67	45.92

776 **5. Conclusion**

777 This paper proposes a novel structured pruning method for the compres-
778 sion of RNN networks. Differently from other approaches that prune weights
779 based on their magnitudes and without taking into consideration the posi-
780 tion of the weights in the RNN matrices, the proposed method treats the
781 rows and columns of the RNN matrices as time-evolving signals that can be
782 modelled using LDS descriptors. In this way, signals with similar temporal
783 dynamics can be pruned without affecting the performance of the pruned
784 model. During fine-tuning, a discrimination-aware variation of the L2 regu-
785 larization is introduced to shrink the magnitude of weights that show limited
786 contribution to the RNN output. Finally, a novel iterative fine-tuning scheme
787 is proposed, in which bigger models guide increasingly smaller ones as a way
788 to bypass the problem of performance degradation when network pruning is
789 performed in a single step.

790 Directions for future work include the use of the proposed method to
791 prune other well-known deep learning architectures and models, such as
792 CNNs and Transformer networks, the assessment of performance gains of
793 pruned models in real-life mobile applications and the pruning of models
794 that process other types of sequence data, such as video and audio.

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